

Annex 1: Replication Roadmap Checklist

Based on the above reports, the following minimum checklist is prepared to help guide actors and interested parties in scheduling, organising, and documenting their activities with regards to implementing a bio-based solid waste management solution in humanitarian settings, based on the Bio4HUMAN experience.

Table 1 Replication Roadmap Checklist

Step	Key Questions	Y/N
<p>Define the replication objective and scope</p>	<p>Specify whether the replication target is a technology (biogas/BSF), a consumable product substitution (compostable RUTF sachets, biodegradable mosquito nets) or a logistics/procurement replacement (adhesive tape, laminating film). Also, confirm the intended setting (e.g. urban, rural, camp-like, etc.) and the waste stream to be addressed and confirm whether the proposed alternative can provide equivalent functionality.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Baseline the current practice and end-of-life pathway</p>	<p>Map what the solution will replace and what currently happens at end of life, including existing waste management responsibilities, service providers, and informal actors. RUTF sachets: littering vs bring-back systems and incineration, mosquito nets: reuse/repurposing and disposal, bags: reuse culture and lack of composting). Identify where environmental benefits depend on missing systems and identify existing SWM/EoL systems available for this solution in the area.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Rapid feasibility screen using stakeholder perceptions</p>	<p>Apply the report's evaluation dimensions to quickly assess perceived feasibility: prior experience, barriers, enablers, stakeholder priorities and concerns, and conditions for adoption. Use solution-specific findings plus cross-cutting themes to identify red flags early (cost sensitivity for RUTF packaging, water constraints for BSF, ownership/exit concerns for community biogas systems, operational risks such as water availability or supply chain fragility), review available</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>

	evidence of lower environmental/social impacts and assess energy consumption in relation to the country energy mix.	
Assess financing and affordability	Use the LCC tool to compare expected costs, identify major cost drivers, assess affordability, similarities in pricing, and determine potential funding sources, including donor support, public-private partnerships, or revenue-generating models where relevant.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Design the delivery model	Select an implementation model consistent with the report's evidence: household, institutional (schools/hospitals/health facilities), cooperative/community cost-sharing (VSLA model), or enterprise/service model (Kaku Sanitation Services). Define who owns, operates, and maintains the solution, including long-term financing and cost-recovery arrangements where relevant, assess local value-chain potential, including raw materials, local production, and local EoL management.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Secure approvals and align with procurement/standards	Where solutions enter humanitarian supply chains or regulated health programming, engage early with clusters, UN agencies, and government authorities. Bio4Human results highlight the need to comply with procurement rules and global standards (WHO, UNICEF Supply Division, Codex Alimentarius) and, for health products, national approvals as needed (mosquito nets require Ministry of Health testing/approval before distribution).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Pilot with demonstration + behaviour change	Run a pilot that includes a hands-on demonstration and sensitization (especially for unfamiliar solutions), an operational testing under real conditions (transport durability, storage temperatures, humidity, wash resistance), and feedback loops with communities and operational teams, and monitoring and documentation of lessons learned and validate equivalent functionality	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

	and operational performance under field conditions.	
Establish monitoring, evaluation and learning arrangements	Define indicators, responsibilities, reporting arrangements, feedback mechanisms, and learning review processes before scaling.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Verify ethical safeguards	Confirm informed consent procedures, community engagement arrangements, data protection measures, food competition, feedback and complaints mechanisms, and protection considerations for vulnerable groups.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Adapt, scale, and institutionalize	Scale only after addressing the adoption conditions identified by stakeholders. Institutionalize through integration into government systems and programmes, a commercially viable business model, or a clear handover arrangement.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No